

An app for finding Personal home fitness trainers

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Abstract:

Technology has a genuine interest in resolving a wide range of human problems, especially now, given the rapid pace of change around the world and the large amount of data available, and it has made inter-personal connections easier. Humans have made countless technical improvements that have helped people save time and effort in their lives. Nobody can deny the importance of fitness in our everyday lives and how it really enhances the overall physical and mental health of a single person as well as society. However, there are a number of obstacles in our regular busy lives, like transportation, relying on someone to take care of kids, lack of motivation, etc., which prevent us from taking that step to reach our fitness goals by working out in a gym or club on a regular basis. Finding a personal trainer using a mobile application and exercising at home can be an excellent answer to this problem, which is now on the rise. This is a great substitute for anyone, regardless of their everyday circumstances, because it encourages them to do most of the workouts they've been doing at the gym at home, at work, or wherever they're most comfortable. This application would benefit people who find it difficult to get to the gym to exercise and participate in physical activities. This application allows the user to select a fitness trainer based on the type of exercise, gender, nationality, and experience.

Individual performance goals, such as weight loss and fitness maintenance, are also tracked by this app. Users can pick between monthly and annual subscriptions, as well as whether they wish to join as a small group of friends or as an individual, which affects the cost. This software also assists users in finding a nutritionist who can assist them with food intake and supplementation for general health and fitness. This application will be available in both English and Arabic.